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**A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE EMPOWERMENT WITH REFERENCE TO TULASI
SEEDS PRIVATE LIMITED, GUNTUR, ANDHRA PRADESH**

T.Sita Ramaiah,
Research Scholar,
Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur
University, Nagpur, Maharashtra

Dr. R.A. Raut,
Assistant Professor,
G.S.College of Commerce,
Wardha, Nagpur, Maharashtra

The success of any organization depends on the availability of committed human resources. Employees with intrinsic motivation perform in a better way than with extrinsic motivation. Now –a – days due to the change in the philosophy of employer’s views towards their employees, they were treated as important variables in the success of the organization. Here we have to remember that the famous saying, “Satisfied employee is a production employee”. Every organization is trying to the best of its efforts to keep the level of satisfaction of employees at a higher degree. Besides providing satisfaction an advanced concept in the current day human resource management discipline to increase the commitment, dedication, morale, belongingness, positive attitude towards organization, creativity and innovative in the task performance and acceptance to any kind of change is ‘Empowerment’.

Empowerment of employees is the responsibility of top-level management. If empowerment programmed is existing in the organization there we can see employees working with higher satisfaction and to the fullest extent. Empowerment can be achieved by involving employees in decision making, accepting and implementing the creative and innovative ideas,

free flow of upward and downward communication, giving freedom in decision making, periodic appraisals by superiors and encouraging the career development programs.

In order to get the benefits from the workers' side every organization is giving priority for the concept of 'Empowerment'.

Scope of the Study:

Empowerment is one of the important objectives of Human Resource Management. Most of the organization now-a-days recognized the importance of empowerment and trying their level best to improve it. Empowerment fully occurs when employees feel competent and valued, when the organization provides opportunities to them to use their talents and when their jobs have meaning and impact. Many employees today are actively seeking opportunities at work to become involved in relevant decisions, thereby contributing their talents and ideas to the organization's success. They hunger for the chance to share what they know and to learn from experience. Consequently, organizations need to provide opportunities for meaningful involvement. This can be achieved through 'Employee Empowerment' – a practical that will result in mutual benefit for both parties. Empowerment is the powerful technique, which releases the hidden talents of the employees. The present study has been undertaken to know the extent of empowerment existing in the organization.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the profile of Tulasi Seeds Private Limited
- To find out degree of empowerment existing in Tulasi Seeds Private Limited
- To study the areas where empowerment is strong and to identify the areas where empowerment is to be improved.
- To analyze the role of management in promoting empowerment.
- To know the satisfaction level of the employees.

Research Methodology

Research Methodology is a systematic and objective process of identifying and formulating the problem by setting objective and methods for collecting, editing, tabulating, evaluating, analyzing, interpreting and presenting data in order to find justified solution.

Research Design

A Research Design is a purely and simply the framework or plan for a study that guides the collection and analysis of data. It is a blue print that is followed in completing a study. The research design undertaken by the researcher is descriptive research design. The methodology involved in this design is mostly qualitative in nature. Descriptive research design is concerned with the research studies with a focus on the portrayal of the characteristics of a group or individual or a situation. The main objective of such studies is to acquire knowledge. Similarly, such studies are used to examine the characteristics of the corporate sector or consumer behavior etc., the descriptive study is typically concerned with determining frequency with which something occurs or how two variables vary together.

Sources of Data Collection:

Data refers to the information or facts. Often researchers understand by data only numerical figures. It also includes descriptive facts, non-numerical information, qualitative and qualitative information. The source of data can be from primary and secondary.

a) Primary Data

Primary data are those data, which are collected as fresh and for the just time and thus happen to be original primary data for this study was collected by preparing a well-structured questionnaire.

b) Secondary Data

Secondary data are those data, which are collected from the already existing information through reference. The secondary data collected by analyzing various materials like Company profiles, Magazines, Journals, Past records and reports and Websites, etc.,

The Sample constituted of 50 employees from different department of the organization.

Method of Sampling

There are many sample methods to collect data. The sampling method used is simple random sampling.

Sample Size:

The Sample constituted of 50 employees from different department of the organizations.

Survey Design:

The survey is based on the primary source of data. Three methods of primary data were selected to conduct the study i.e., Questionnaire, Observation and Personal Interviews. Since the statements in the Questionnaire and Schedule were qualitative, they are quantified on a five-point Scale using Linker type technique. Respondents are asked to tick mark the appropriate scope on a five-point continuum.

Statistical Tools For The Study:

1. Sample Analysis By Percentage (%) Method:

% refers to a special kind of ratio. % is used in making comparison between two or more series of data, % are used to describe relationship. It can be used to compare the relative terms, the distribution of two or more series of data.

$$\text{(No. of respondents / Total No. of Sample Size)} * 100$$

2. Weighted Arithmetic mean

However, in practice, we might come across situations where the relative importance of all the items of the distribution is not the same. If some items in a distribution are more important than others, then this point must be borne in mind. In order that average is computed is representative of the distribution. In such cases, proper weightage is to be given to the various items.

The weights attached to each item being proportional to the importance of the items in the distribution. Weighted arithmetic mean gives the relative importance of the different items in the distribution. In order to avoid the bias in the calculation of a representative value of a series or distribution we use weighted arithmetic mean. It is denoted by the symbol w_e .

Formula to calculate weighted arithmetic mean

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{We} &= \frac{w_1x_1 + w_2x_2 + w_3x_3 + \dots + w_nx_n}{w_1 + w_2 + w_3 + \dots + w_n} \\
 &= \frac{\sum w_{ax}}{\sum w}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n is the respective weights of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n .

Grades:

Strongly agree = 5, agree = 4, agree to some extend = 3, disagree = 2, strongly disagree = 1.

Plan of Analysis:

The data, which was collected from the respondents through a structured questionnaire, was organized, processed and tabulated on a data sheet. Separate tables were furnished under specific headings. They were analyzed with the help of statistical analysis techniques in order to interpret the data and draw conclusions. Graphs were also drawn to depict a clear picture of findings and conclusions.

Limitations Of The Study:

As the study includes the gathering of individual’s opinions, the results were prepared based on the personal opinions.

1. Due to the personal bias the opinions of the employees may be distorted and it is limitation.
2. As the time for the research is limited, there is no chance for collecting opinions from more employees.
3. As some employees are busy in their job activities, they use to refuse to give their opinions.

Profile Of Tulasi Seeds Private Limited

Tulasi Seeds Private Limited was incorporated on 15th May, 1992 under the proprietorship of Sri Tulasi Ram Chandra Prabhu. TSPL is one among the industries which are being run under the same management.

Coastal Packaging was the first industry started by them in the year 1977. Later on Chaitanya Packaging Private Limited and Chandra Transport Agency were started in 1988. After that White Gold Chits & Finance came into existence. This institution holds 50 percent of total number of shares of Tulasi Seeds Private Limited.

The company was started with an initial investment of Rs. 2 lakhs. In the initial stage, it has no processing plant. In the year 1994, it has set up a processing plant equipped with full machinery. Thirty acres of land is being cultivated under the ownership of the company. The company has arranged their own laboratory in the current financial year. Previously they had no such facility and they had faced expensive testing.

The company proprietor, Sir Tulasi Ramachandra Prabhu, had received “Best Management Award” in 1994 from the hands of Former Chief Minister, Mr. Kotla Vijaya Bhaskar Reddy. Again in this year, he received “Parisramika Vijetha 2002” award from the Minister of Industries, Mr. Kotagiri Vidyadhar. The company is being run under his efficient management in such a way that it is not only to pave its way but also able to earn some surplus to meet the needs of growth and expansion.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Empowerment:

To compute the weighted arithmetic mean for empowerment, we have to take the ‘ $\sum Wi$ ’ values for all the factors that are taken to know the extent of empowerment with respect to the grades (5,4,3,2,1) represented by ‘ Xi ’.

GRADES: $X_1=5, X_2=4, X_3=3, X_4=2, X_5=1$

WEIGHTS: W_1, W_2, W_3, W_4, W_5

Weights with respect to grades regarding seven factors are given below

GRADES	5	4	3	2	1
Q.NO	W1	W2	W3	W4	W5
1	44	70	54	30	2
11	60	74	40	16	10
111	36	70	62	24	8
1V	12	62	44	20	12
V	48	54	34	12	2
V1	16	44	26	6	8
$\sum W_i$	216	374	260	108	42
%	21	37	26	10	4

$$\sum W_i = \sum W_1 + \sum W_2 + \sum W_3 + \sum W_4 + \sum W_5 = 1000$$

$$\sum W_i X_i = 216*5 + 374*4 + 260*3 + 108*2 + 42*1 = 3614$$

$$\sum W_i X_i / \sum W_i = 3614 / 1000 = 3.614$$

The above table shows 37 of respondents at ‘agree’ level regarding ‘Empowerment’ while 10% and 4% of respondents are at ‘disagree’ and ‘strongly disagree’ levels respectively.

The Weighted Arithmetic Mean calculated regarding the Empowerment is 3.614.

Findings:

- The employees belonging to Tulasi Seeds Private Limited, regarding ‘Empowerment’ is positive and satisfactory.

- Majority of the employees accepted that they are encouraged to participate in decision-making.
- Most of the employees accepted that the communication system was well developed in the Tulasi Seeds Private Limited.
- Among the respondents 14% and 48% of employees are at 'Strongly Agree' level and 'Agree' level respectively, who accepted that their creative and innovation ideas are encouraged and recognized by the Tulasi Seeds Private Limited.
- Among respondents, 7% and 57% of employees are at 'Strongly Agree' level and 'Agree' level respectively, who accepted that there is favorable organization culture and climate, which helps to achieve the individual goals as well as organization.
- Majority of the employees accepted that they are having authority and responsibility regarding their job activities.
- Most of the employees accepted that the management is undertaking excellent motivation techniques to motivate the employees.
- Majority of the employees accepted that there is good cooperation between work groups and colleagues.

Suggestions:

- Tulasi Seeds Private Limited is encouraging decision making & innovative ideas, it is better for the organization to maintain the same existing system.
- Organization adopted motivation techniques like reward system, incentives, promotion and they have to implement new techniques like cash prize for the star performer of the organization.
- Some of the employees are working with graduation qualification only, the organization should encourage them to enroll into courses like, M.Tech, MBA for their career development.
- Keeping in view the significance of good relationship between employers and employees, the organization is paying attention to develop these relationships under certain existing framework. To intensify these relationships other activities like helping the employees in

their private life, moral support under certain unforeseen consequences, participating in various cultural activities are also to be practiced.

Conclusion:

Tulasi Seeds Private Limited management is trying to the level best of its efforts to keep the level of satisfaction of employees at a higher degree. The employees commitment to work, dedication, morale, belongingness, positive attitude towards organization, creativity and innovative in the task performance was improved because of Employee Empowerment.

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